

PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PROFESSIONAL AND MENTAL HEALTH: ANALYSIS OF WESTERN AND NATIONAL PARADIGMS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the issue of professional health and mental stability based on Western psychological schools and national approaches of Uzbekistan. Along with psychoanalytic, humanistic, cognitive-stress and activity theories, the concept of "psychological immunity" that is being formed in national psychology is also studied. The article highlights professional stability as one of the internal determinants of mental health and offers an integrative analysis of international and national paradigms.

In modern society, a person's professional activity is one of the most important factors determining his quality of life, social status and mental stability. Changes in working conditions, increased competitive environment, increased information flow and increased psychological pressure make the issue of professional health of a person an urgent problem. Especially in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the modernization of the labor market, the expansion of freedom of choice of profession and the increase in demand for human resources require a person to be responsible, stable and motivationally prepared for his professional activity.

Today, along with a person's physical health, professional health is considered an important psychological indicator expressing the level of his professional stability, psychological adaptation and job satisfaction. While in Western psychology this issue is studied mainly through individual mechanisms - stress management, needs satisfaction, identification processes, in Uzbek psychology this problem is studied in the context of moral, spiritual and social values.

Z. Freud in the psychoanalytic approach explains professional activity as a mechanism that transforms a person's libidinal energy into a socially acceptable direction - sublimation. When a person cannot direct his inner instincts in a positive direction, mental stress and neuroses arise. Thus, professional activity is a means of psychological protection that stabilizes mental health.[1]

In the theory of A. Adler, professional choice is an expression of the desire to eliminate the "sense of inferiority" in a person and bring social benefit. A profession is a means for a person to feel useful in society, to increase self-confidence.[2]

In the theory of E. Erikson's psychosocial development, the "identity crisis" is interpreted as a stage of determining the professional role of a person. Through a profession, a person learns social values and achieves self-realization.[3]

According to A. Maslow's theory of the hierarchy of needs, mental health is associated with self-actualization, the realization of personal abilities. Profession is a field for realizing a person's inner potential.[4]

K. Rogers, in his person-centered approach, explains mental stability as the harmony between the 'real self' and the 'ideal self'. Professional activity is seen as a psychological process that ensures this harmony.[5]

R. Lazarus, in his theory of cognitive appraisal of stress, emphasizes the importance of how a person interprets a stressful situation and chooses strategies to adapt to it. Constructive coping mechanisms play an important role in maintaining mental health.[6]

H. Selye, in his theory of stress physiology, showed that constant professional stress leads to the syndrome of 'professional burnout'. He introduced the difference between eustress and distress and justified the need to ensure their balance in order to maintain mental health.[7]

In Uzbek psychology, issues of professional health are studied in the context of cultural, moral and spiritual values. The mental stability of a person is assessed not only through the criteria of emotional, but also social and spiritual harmony. While in the West the main emphasis is on stress, motivation and emotional exhaustion, in the national approach such indicators as mental immunity, moral responsibility and social appreciation occupy a central place.

Professor S. Karimova's concept of "Psychological immunity" is a new theoretical basis for Uzbek psychology, providing stress resistance based on the internal resources of the individual. This immune system includes emotional stability, religious strength, moral principles and professional responsibility [8].

In Western psychology, the approach to this issue is mainly expressed through individual and cognitive mechanisms. For example, Z. Freud and A. Adler saw professional activity as a form of compensation for the internal needs of the individual, while R. Lazarus and H. Selye analyzed the mechanisms of stress management, adaptation and professional burnout syndrome. A. Maslow and K. Rogers interpret mental health as a process of self-awareness of the individual, realization of his potential and achieving internal harmony. Thus, in the Western paradigm, professional health is the process of achieving stability in work through the effective management of the internal psychic resources of the individual.

In contrast, Uzbek psychology approaches this issue in the context of cultural, spiritual and moral values. In national research, the basis of professional health is the social responsibility, spiritual purity and moral stability of the individual. Professor S. Karimova's concept of "psychological immunity" is considered as a psychic system based on faith and moral foundations that protects the internal mental stability of the individual, provides resistance to stress. This approach considers it important that the individual manifests himself in professional activities not only professionally, but also humanly and spiritually.

Thus, while the Western paradigm focuses more on individual psychological processes - cognitive assessment, stress management, motivation and self-awareness, the national paradigm sees moral values, religious stability, social responsibility and spiritual harmony as the main determinants.

Therefore, the integration of both approaches in the study of professional health is the most effective scientific direction. The integrative model analyzes the cognitive, emotional, moral, and cultural aspects of a person together. This approach allows us to study the individual not only as a labor subject, but also as a social being formed in a system of spiritual values.

In order to study occupational health in more depth in the future:

1. Development of psychodiagnostic tools appropriate to the national-cultural context;
2. Study of the relationship between occupational stress and psychological immunity on an empirical basis;
3. It is necessary to create a comprehensive model that combines Western theories with the cultural values of Uzbekistan.

The analysis of Western and national approaches shows that occupational health is a complex psychological system that reflects the mental, social and spiritual stability of a person. While Western approaches highlight individual and cognitive mechanisms, Uzbek psychology interprets mental health based on moral and spiritual values. In the future, the development of psychodiagnostic tools appropriate to the national context and the integration of international theories in this direction will remain a scientifically relevant task.

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